

USING SOME NUTRIENTS AND ESSENTIAL OILS FOR IMPROVING 'CRIMSON SEEDLESS' GRAPES COLOR

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ABSTRACT

The climate in Egypt is cool winters and hot dry summer. 'Crimson seedless' is a table grape under certain environmental conditions, the fruit exhibits inadequate red color development, causing economic losses due to lower product quality even after they have been treated with ethephon. Essential oils are extracted from the flowers, barks, stems, leaves, roots, fruits, and other parts of the plant by various methods. Essential oils in general are used as antimicrobial and antioxidant and also have pharmacological effects been described in pharmacopeias. In this paper, we discuss the effect of essential oils also in coloring. The use of plant growth regulators, such as Absciscic (ABA) and boric acids during development increases the anthocyanin content of the skin, improving the color of the berry. In the current study, a randomized block design was used and treatments included the application of ten different pre-harvest. Treatments were: Control (C), 1% Boric acid (BA), 2% Boric acid (BA), 1% Absciscic acid (ABA), 2% Absciscic acid (ABA), 1% Rosemary oil (RO), 2% Rosemary oil (RO), 1% camphor oil (CO), 2% camphor oil (CO), 2% ethephon. Clusters were sprayed twice. The first one was in the version stage, the second application was performed for all treatments, 15 days after the first application, except for the control. On harvest day 3 clusters per treatment were taken at random for the determination of harvest physical and chemical properties and compared with clusters which storage at room temperature as a market condition. Grapes treated with Absciscic acid 1% or Boric acid 1% or Camphor oil 2% could be harvested 15 - 30 days before controlling grapes because of their advanced color development and that due to lower costs by reducing the number of harvests. Due to the need for an economic alternative for table grape production, Clusters had a great consumer acceptance through visual sensory analysis such as firmness, total soluble solids (TSS), titratable acidity (TA), the index of maturation (TSS/TA), and total polyphenols of berries and quality in marketing.

Keywords: Crimson Seedless, Grape, Absciscic acid, Boric acid, Rosemary oil, Camphor oil

INTRODUCTION

Grape (*Vitis vinifera* L.) is considered one of the oldest known edible fruits mentioned in the Bible and Quran. Grapes grown under warm climate conditions tend to show less color development, and this phenomenon is attributed to low anthocyanin accumulation in berry skin in response to high temperatures during ripening. 'Benitaka' (*Vitis vinifera* L.) is a table grape that shows poor color development when grown under a subtropical condition, In part, this is due to high night temperatures that inhibit the accumulation of anthocyanin(Muhammad et al 2020).High temperatures at the beginning of grape ripening may decrease the levels of absciscic acid (ABA), and during this process may reduce piling up of anthocyanin and increase their degradation (Koshita et al., 2015).Anthocyanin is synthesized by the phenylpropanoid pathway; several structural genes and encoding enzymes of this pathway have been well described (Villegas et al., 2016).Accumulation of anthocyanin begins at veraison, this accumulation appears to be related to the actions of two endogenous

PGRs, auxins which inhibit anthocyanin synthesis, and abscisic acid (ABA) which enhances anthocyanin accumulation (Ban et al., 2003; Lund et al., 2008; Ferrara et al., 2015;).The gathering of anthocyanin in the grape skin is stimulated by the exogenous application of sugar (Olivares, et al 2017). Application of ethephon can increase the assemblage of anthocyanin, while also advancing ripening (Lichter et al., 2004). Ethephon is also usually applied to red-colored Table grapes to improve berry color. Moreover, ethephon application can cause berry softening, which reduces the value of exported grapes (Peppi et al., 2007). Therefore, it is necessary to identify other cost-effective management practices capable of enhancing berry color, without causing excessive softening. During plant evolution, ABA conserved cellular responses modulation to stimuli affecting the cell water status, and regulation of different processes, sometimes also in a species-specific way (Takezawa et al., 2011; Wanke, 2011). Boric acid is used for sterilization and disinfection. Due to its disinfectant, bactericidal, and wall strengthening properties boric acid reduces the postharvest rotting in many fruits. Boron can be involved in several pathways and can act in the regulation of metabolic processes that looks like plant hormones(Lovatt and Dugger, 1984).(Besong and Lawanson 1991) confirmed that the activity of respiratory enzymes was concentrated under boron deficiency, but lowered by boron application. Ethylene production in boron-treated fruit was reduced, most effectively after boron and calcium application.

The functions of boron and calcium on the structure of cell walls and cell membranes. Essential oils are volatile, natural, complex compounds characterized by a strong odor and are formed by aromatic plants as secondary metabolites. Essential oils are also aromatic oily liquids obtained by steam or hydro distillation from plant materials such as flowers, buds, seeds, leaves, twigs, bark, herbs, wood, fruits, and roots. An estimated 3000 Essential oils are known, of which about 300 are commercially important (Solgi1 and Ghorbanpour 2014). Essential oils have an antimicrobial and antioxidant function which could greatly aid in the protraction of the shelf life of fresh-cut products (Valero et al., 2006; Serrano et al., 2008).Lee et al. (2005) identified the aromatic compounds of different essential oils, such as thymol, carvacrol, 4-aliphenol and eugenol showed a high level of antioxidant activity, inhibiting hexanal oxidation by 95-99% at 5 µ/mL over 30 days. Genetic characteristics of the plants as well as the conditions under which they are grown are effective inthe chemical composition of Eucalyptus olida (Gillesetl 2010).The genus Lavandula (lavender) is comprised of about 25–30 species of flowering plants is known as anessential oil for its antimicrobial and antifungal characteristics (D’auria,et al., 2005). In general, cytotoxicity of EOs is mostly due to alcohols, phenols, and aldehydes. (Bakkali et al, 2008).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Grapevines and growing conditions

The study was conducted during the years 2019 and 2020 in the Experimental Farm of Mansoura Research Station on Crimson seedless grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L.,) spaced at 4 × 2 m and trained in a pergola system. Vines were 8 years old growing in clay soil.A randomized complete block design was used as a statistical model with ten treatments and four

replications, each plot consisting of one grapevine. The crop management practices adopted for plant nutrition, weed control, and pest and disease management were those commonly used in the region.

Treatments and experimental design

The treatments were applied by spraying only the clusters in the morning, using a knapsack sprayer with hollow cone spray nozzles JA1, providing complete and uniform coverage. Treatments, applied on different timings of ripening were tested: the first one at version (V); and the second at post version (POV) (at 7 days after V).

Treatments were:

- 1-Control (C), 2- 10 g/L Boric acid (BA) 3 – 20 g/L Boric acid (BA)
- 4-10 g/L Absciscic acid (ABA)5 – 20 g/L Absciscic acid (ABA)
- 6- 10 g /L, Rosemary oil (RO) 7- 20 g/L Rosemary oil (RO)
- 8- 10 g/L camphor oil (CO)9- 20 g /L camphor oil (CO)10- 20 m/ L ethephon.

When berries were in the ripening stage (S.S.C $\approx$ 14 – 15 %) and (0.4 – 0.5 %) acidity and complete red color of berries skin clusters hand-harvest the clusters of all treatments were harvested on the same day. In the summer season, the harvest was performed in early September. 5 clusters per vine were taken at random for the determination of harvest physical and chemical properties.

Physical parameters cluster weight (g), berry firmness (g/cm) using a grapes pressure tester.

Chemical parameters

Soluble solids content (S.S.C): were determined in the berries using a digital refractometer (Model PR-32, Atago, Japan) by squeezing the fruit (**A. O. A. C., 1984**).

Total acidity: was determined by titration with a standard solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1N), using phenolphthalein as an indicator (**A. O. A. C., 1984**). The results were expressed as percentages of anhydrous tartaric acid according to the following equation:

$$\text{Total acidity (\%)} = \frac{\text{ml of NaOH} \times 0.0074 \times 100}{\text{ml juice used}}$$

S.S.C/acid ratio was also determined.

Total anthocyanin concentration in the grape berry skin was performed according to a method described by (**Peppi et al.2006**). From each sample, 3g of the berry skin was peeled off and washed with distilled water, followed by a quick wash with ionized water, and then dried with sterilized tissues. Further, 30mL acidified methanol (HCl 1% + methanol 99%) was added to the peeled berry skin and kept in the dark for 48 h. The values were recorded using a

spectrophotometer at 520 nm, and the results were expressed as milligrams of total anthocyanin sasmalvidin-3-glucoside per gram of berry skin (mg.g⁻¹).

Total polyphenol concentration in the pulp and skin of berries was based on the FolinCiocalteu method (Bucic-Kojicet al., 2007; Borgesetal., 2013). The samples were macerated and 5g of this sample was homogenized with 50 mL of 50% ethanol in a blender for 2 min and centrifuged at 3500rpm for 5min. A 0.2mL aliquot of the extract was mixed with 1.8 mL distilled water and 10 mL of 10-fold diluted Folin Ciocalteu reagent. In addition, after 30 s to 8 min, 8 mL of 7.5% Na₂CO₃ solution was added. All test tubes containing the mixture were shaken for 10s on the vortex and kept in the darkness for 2h. Further, the absorbance of each sample was measured after 15min using a spectrophotometer at 765nm against a blank sample. Total polyphenols were determined from the calibration curve obtained with gallic acid; readings were expressed as mg.100g⁻¹ of berries (gallic acid equivalents). On harvest day also clusters were packed in carton boxes (2 kg grapes each) three replicates of nine samples from every treatment were taken to be held at room temperature (25-30 °C and R.H 45%) to simulate the marketing period. Samples were examined at 2 days intervals to be objected weight loss %, shattering% unmarketable berries percent, and firmness was detected at 2, 4, and 6 days. S.S.C %, acidity, S.S.C/acidity ratio, and anthocyanin were estimated at harvest and after 6 days (the termination of experiment temperature when 50% or more of pedicles were browning).

The obtained data throughout the two seasons were subjected to analysis of SAS Computer Program (1998) according to Duncan's multiple ranges.

Results and Decoctions

Harvest date

It is known that Crimson seedless grape under Egypt climate harvest at mid of September in the delta. Crimson seedless grapes treated by boric acid, abscisic acid, rosemary oil, camphor oil in their concentration (1%, 2%) and ethephon 2%, clusters of grapes attained marketable quality between the first week to the third week of August depending on the treatments they received. Grapes treated colored quickly and thus were harvestable earlier than untreated grapes.

Physical quality attributes

Insoluble protopectin breakdown into soluble pectin by the cellular disintegration leading to increased or membrane permeability due to softening of fruits (Mattoet, al., 1975). Tables 1 and 2 show a significant decrease in berry firmness and increase on shatter berries at the end of the trial for all treatments in the two seasons for all treatments and increasing concentration to 2% in boric or abscisic acids or essential oils (rosemary and camphor) not more effective. We noticed that rosemary oil 2% and camphor oil 2% were in the line of boric acid and abscisic acid with no significant difference between them while the concentration in 1% for two oils has no significant difference with ethephon 2%. The reduction in fruit softening with the boric acid application may be due to a decrease in

Physiological loss in weight (PLW) and cell wall degenerating enzyme (PME) activity(Kaur et al., 2016). While Anthocyanin accumulation by Abscisic acid which due to implying these compounds are stored inside the cell vacuole, thus increasing the solute concentration. As water flows from the area of low concentration towards the area of high concentration the cell vacuole must have absorbed more water from the surrounding cytoplasm and decreased the cell turgidity. This could be the reason behind the decrease in the firmness of grape berries in response to S-ABA treatments.(Muhammad et al., 2020). Regulated ofS-ABAdecreasing the shatter as affected by hormonal balance controls the senescence process(Ferrara et al., 2016).

Table 1: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils on Crimson Seedless Grape in Berry Firmness Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

Berry firmness (ib/in ²)										
Season	2019					2020				
Period in days										
Treatments	H	2	4	6		H	2	4	6	
T ₁	9.3 a	9.2 a	8.5 c	6.8 f		9.8 a	9.5 a	8.8 b	7.3 e	
T ₂	9.3 a	9.3 a	8.6 c	8.0 d		9.6 a	9.5 a	9.1 b	8.2 c	
T ₃	9.2 a	9.1 ab	8.6 c	7.9 d		9.5 a	9.4 a	8.9 b	8.0 c	
T ₄	9.3 a	9.1 ab	8.5 c	7.7 e		9.7 a	9.5 a	9.0 b	8.0 c	
T ₅	9.2 a	9.0 ab	8.6 c	7.7 e		9.4 a	9.2 ab	8.4 c	7.8 c	
T ₆	9.4 a	9.1 ab	8.5 c	7.7 e		9.6 a	9.3 a	8.8 b	8.0 c	
T ₇	9.0 ab	9.0 ab	8.5 d	7.5 f		9.4 a	9.2 a	8.6 c	7.8 d	
T ₈	9.0 ab	9.0 ab	8.2 d	7.5 f		9.3 a	9.0 b	8.5 c	7.8 d	
T ₉	9.0 ab	8.9 b	8.0 d	7.7 e		9.2 ab	9.0 b	8.6 c	7.8 d	
T ₁₀	9.0 ab	8.8 b	8.0 d	7.1 f		9.7 a	9.3 a	8.5 c	7.5 e	

T₁ = control

T₂ = boric acid 1%

T₃ = boric acid 2%

T₄ = abscisic acid 1%

T₅ = abscisic acid 2%

T₆ = rosemary oil 1%

T₇ = rosemary 2%

T₈ = camphor oil 1%

T₉ = camphor 2%

T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

Table 2: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils on ‘Crimson Seedless’ Grape in Berry Shatter Percentage Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

Shatter (%)							
Season	2019			2020			
Period in days							
Treatments	2	4	6		2	4	6
T ₁	2.06 h	5.03 e	10.50 a		2.54 m	5.95 f	11.32 a
T ₂	0.41 l	2.16 h	5.06 e		0.34 r	2.68 m	4.74 j
T ₃	0.19 m	2.00 h	5.56 d		0.68 q	2.25 m	4.38 I
T ₄	0.56 k	3.83 g	6.60 d		0.98 p	3.67 k	7.88 d
T ₅	1.04 j	3.40 g	6.56 d		1.76 n	4.14 j	6.93 e
T ₆	1.74 i	4.60 f	9.50 b		1.91 n	4.84 i	10.12 b
T ₇	1.93 i	4.66 f	8.30 c		3.03 l	4.97 h	9.38 c
T ₈	1.70 i	4.83 d	9.66 b		2.38 m	5.87 f	10.00 b
T ₉	2.00 h	4.91 f	8.46 c		2.29 m	6.66 e	9.27 c
T ₁₀	0.83 k	3.50 g	9.30 b		1.33 o	5.72 g	10.16 b

- T₁ = control
- T₂ = boric acid 1%
- T₃ = boric acid 2%
- T₄ = abscisic acid 1%
- T₅ = abscisic acid 2%
- T₆ = rosemary oil 1%
- T₇ = rosemary 2%
- T₈ = camphor oil 1%
- T₉ = camphor 2%
- T₁₀ = ethaphon 2%

Metabolic activity, respiration, and transpiration due to loss in weight according to (Yaman 2002). Respiration diffusion of water vapor pressure is a reason for moisture loss from fresh fruits and vegetables. (Jawandha, et al., 2012). Ethaphon 2% and abscisic acid were reduced loss in weight in the first season where abscisic was 1% and in second season abscisic 2%, (Table 3). While according to decayed berries Ethaphon 2% and control treatments had a great value for decayed berries and the best treatment reducing decay was boric 2% for two seasons (Table 4). Decay percentage increased as the advancing of shelf life period in the two seasons of study. Rosemary 2% reduced decayed berries as similar to abscisic acid in two concentrations without any difference. It could be due to activating enzymatic carbohydrate synthesis during berry development. Therefore, the activation processes such as the Calvin cycle, the pentose phosphate, and the Glycolysis pathway might constitute the increased sugar content in berry development. So, total sugars increased (Glucose and fructose) which could be a precursor toward increasing AA synthesis in berry juice. The increases of TP might be explained that the increases of AA berry content by which maintaining the amount

of TP as antioxidant properties also, cyanocobalamin may modulate the active oxygen) species(Lo'ay, 2017).

Table 3: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils on loss in weight percentage on Crimson Seedless Grape at Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

Loss in weight (%)							
Season	2019				2020		
Period in days							
Treatments	2	4	6		2	4	6
T ₁	3.00 j	5.81 g	11.56 a		2.57h	6.56 d	10.59 a
T ₂	1.88 k	4.48 h	9.75 d		2.01 i	5.46 e	9.88 ab
T ₃	1.06 k	3.48 h	9.63 d		1.93 j	3.06 gh	9.21 b
T ₄	1.34 k	3.65 i	8.59 f		1.95 j	3.06 gh	7.56 d
T ₅	1.76 k	3.48 i	9.79 cd		1.86 j	3.10 g	8.83 c
T ₆	1.90 k	4.24 hi	9.07 e		2.03 i	3.63 g	9.20 b
T ₇	1.37 k	4.25 hi	10.22 b		1.81 j	4.75 ef	9.83 ab
T ₈	1.75 k	4.44 hi	10.74 ab		1.69 j	4.81 ef	9.95 ab
T ₉	1.64 k	4.20 hi	11.12 ab		1.67 j	5.16 e	10.79 a
T ₁₀	1.75 k	3.54 i	8.54 f		1.58 j	4.03 f	8.93 c

- T₁ = control
- T₂ = boric acid 1%
- T₃ = boric acid 2%
- T₄ = abscisic acid 1%
- T₅ = abscisic acid 2%
- T₆ = rosemary oil 1%
- T₇ = rosemary 2%
- T₈ = camphor oil 1%
- T₉ = camphor 2%
- T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

Table 4: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils on Decay Percentage on Crimson Seedless Grape at Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

Decay (%)							
Season	2019			2020			
Period in days							
Treatments	2	4	6		2	4	6
T ₁	1.33 h	4.10 e	8.40 a		0.33 i	1.70	7.46 a
T ₂	0.00 k	1.50 h	5.16 c		0.00 k	1.90 f	4.63 c
T ₃	0.66 j	1.27 h	3.61e		0.00 k	1.36 g	3.33 e
T ₄	0.66 j	1.76 h	4.13 d		0.00 k	1.10 g	4.90 c
T ₅	0.00 k	1.43 h	4.63 d		0.00 k	0.86 h	4.30 d
T ₆	0.83 j	2.26 g	5.20 c		0.17 j	1.70 f	4.41 d
T ₇	0.00 k	2.66 f	4.56 d		0.25 i	1.60 f	4.61 c
T ₈	0.66 j	2.33 g	5.16 c		0.13 j	1.33 g	5.05 c
T ₉	0.00 k	2.00 h	5.86 b		0.00 k	1.03 g	5.35 b
T ₁₀	0.00 k	2.00 h	6.83 b		0.00 k	0.80 h	5.93 b

- T₁ = control
- T₂ = boric acid 1%
- T₃ = boric acid 2%
- T₄ = abscisic acid 1%
- T₅ = abscisic acid 2%
- T₆ = rosemary oil 1%
- T₇ = rosemary 2%
- T₈ = camphor oil 1%
- T₉ = camphor oil 2%
- T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

Chemical quality attributes

We found from Table 5 that essential oils have a good effect on coloring Crimson seedless grapes. Data in both seasons showed highly significant differences among the tested treatments boric and abscisic acids in their concentrations (1%, 2%) have a large value on anthocyanin accumulation flowed by camphor oil (1%, 2%), ethephon 2%, and rosemary oil (1%, 2%) while the control has a lower value. We noticed also that berry color decreased with increasing shelf life. The anthocyanin synthesis pathway causes the color of grape berry skin (Boss, et al., 1996). The increase in anthocyanin follows the increase of enzymes synthesis involved in secondary metabolism (Ban et al., 2003). Maybe the reason for the increasing color of Crimson seedless grapes when using camphor oil or rosemary oil is caused by flavonoids produced by them as suggested by (Denys J. Charles, 2013). Whereas there are several flavonoids and phenolic compounds in rosemary and camphor which promote the improvement of coloring in the grapes. In the first four cell layers in the hypodermis of the berries; and in some cases, in the mesocarp and seeds, anthocyanin accumulates in the

vacuoles of tissue, (Cantos et. al., 2002). Anthocyanins synthesized from the precursor phenylalanine and acetate through the path of phenylpropanoids (Dixon et al., 2005, Winkel, 2004 and Zhang, 2005). Anthocyanin is a metabolic product of flavones and hence is placed in the flavonoids group. Studies on the Kyoho grape cultivar have noticed that genes involved in the path of the phenylpropanoids are stimulated by ABA at the veraison stage. Anthocyanins are synthesized during veraison; a stage that corresponds to a change in color (Keller and Hrazdina 1998). The development of color in the berry skin is also affected by factors such as diurnal temperature, light intensity, berry quality, leaf surface area, shoot length, carbohydrates, mineral nutrition, and plant hormones (Kliwer and Lider 1970, Wheeler, 2009, Zamora et, al., 2003). A stronger correlation exists between anthocyanin and color development, as well as on daily basis. TSS, TA, index of maturation, and total polyphenols were not significantly affected by the use of S-ABA. Similarly, other physical attributes like length, width, and berry mass did not show any significant change. However, berry firmness slightly varied in response to these treatments, but not to the extent where it compromised the berry quality for commercial use. There is a slight difference in berry color between the two seasons evaluated, and this difference is probably due to the different weather conditions in which the ripening.

Boric acid 1% increases total phenols than all treatments flavored by rosemary oil 2% and camphor oil 1%. The application of ABA induces the synthesis of phenolic compounds in grape berries (Dry, 2000; Jeong, 2004. Rufato et al. 2016) applied different doses of ABA to Isabel grapes and found that the concentration of 800 mg L⁻¹ resulted in a 95% increment in the content of polyphenols in berries. These results support the findings in this research with Cabernet Franc. Studies conducted in Chile; had determined that an application of ABA in Crimson grapes five days before the veraison stage, increased the content of sugars and anthocyanins and decreased the acidity in the berries; an effect which is associated with an increasing concentration of phenolic compounds (Villalobos, 2011).

(Daniela et, al., 2017) demonstrated that the applications of ABA and/or sucrose had a significant effect on the development of color, being able to advance the harvest by 37 and 15 days, respectively. Interestingly, this increase in color did not affect other important quality attributes in grapes such as firmness, soluble solids, and acidity, unlike the effects observed with other growth regulators such as ethephon.

Table 5: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils on Total Anthocyanin (mg. g⁻¹) and Total Phenols on Crimson Seedless Grape at Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

Total anthocyanin (mg. g ⁻¹)					Total phenols				
Season	2019		2020		2019		2020		
Period in days									
Treatments	H	6	H	6	H	6	H	6	
T ₁	16.42 f	15.17g	17.69 e	16.22 f	0.45 ab	0.42 bc	0.46 a	0.44 b	
T ₂	20.68 b	18.50 d	20.25 b	18.72 d	0.46 a	0.39 bc	0.46 a	0.42 c	
T ₃	21.39 a	17.87 e	22.25 a	20.13 b	0.42 bc	0.33 c	0.45 ab	0.39 d	
T ₄	20.12 b	17.58 e	19.00 c	16.72 f	0.42 bc	0.38 cd	0.45 ab	0.36 e	
T ₅	20.06 b	17.69 e	20.76 b	19.33 c	0.36 d	0.32 de	0.38 c	0.32 f	
T ₆	19.72 c	17.81 e	19.88 c	17.67 e	0.41bc	0.37 cd	0.44 b	0.39 d	
T ₇	19.96 c	17.29 e	20.01 b	17.68 e	0.44 b	0.39 bc	0.47 a	0.40 c	
T ₈	20.18 b	16.87 f	20.80 b	17.76 e	0.45 ab	0.38 cd	0.48 a	0.37 e	
T ₉	20.17 b	17.85 e	20.39 b	18.00 d	0.39 bc	0.35 d	0.41 b	0.34 f	
T ₁₀	20.60 b	17.31 e	20.28 b	18.44 d	0.45 ab	0.37 cd	0.46 a	0.41 b	

- T₁ = control
- T₂ = boric acid 1%
- T₃ = boric acid 2%
- T₄ = abscisic acid 1%
- T₅ = abscisic acid 2%
- T₆ = rosemary oil 1%
- T₇ = rosemary 2%
- T₈ = camphor oil 1%
- T₉ = camphor 2%
- T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

All treatments have no effect on S.S.C or acidity or maturation index (SS.C / acid), as shown in Tables 6 and 8. The increase in S.S.C with the advancement of the storage period may be due to the numerous catabolic processes taking place in the fruits during ripening and senescence processes. The increase in T.S.S could also be attributed to water loss, hydrolysis of starch, and other polysaccharides to the soluble form of sugar (Wills, et, al., 1980). (Bhakareet al. 2006) reported increasing S.S.C values and decreasing acidity values with increasing boric acid treatments. Whoever (Biliret, al., 2018) accused that maturity index is an important gauge for assessing in this respect. 0.1% boric acid dose was found to be most

suitable in terms of the maturity index. The soluble solid content consistently increased throughout the process of berry ripening (Marquette, et, al., 1999; Reynier 2002, Tesic, et, al., 2001). There is a rapid accumulation of sugar in the berries from the veraison stage due to the migration of photosynthetic products through the grape bunches. Additionally, sugar reserves such as fructose are also mobilized through the shoots and root system. (Ball, 1997) indicated that the decrease in acidity of fruits is a result of the breakup of acids to sugars during respiration.

Table 6: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils for Soluble Solid Content on Crimson Seedless Grape at Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

S.S.C									
Season	2019					2020			
Period in days									
Treatments	H	2	4	6		H	2	4	6
T ₁	15.6 b	16.1 ab	16.3 ab	16.8 ab		15.8ab	16.0 ab	16.3 ab	17.0 a
T ₂	16.3 ab	16.5 ab	16.9 ab	17.1 ab		15.6 b	15.9 ab	16.2 ab	16.6 a
T ₃	15.8 b	16.0 ab	16.0 ab	16.2 ab		15.3 b	15.6 b	16.0 ab	17.0 a
T ₄	15.6 b	16.0 ab	16.8 ab	17.3 a		15.9ab	16.1 ab	16.3 ab	17.0 a
T ₅	15.5 b	15.7b	16.3 ab	16.8 ab		15.6 b	16.0 ab	16.3 ab	17.0 a
T ₆	16.0 ab	16.3 ab	16.5 ab	17.0 a		15.6 b	15.9 ab	16.3 ab	17.0 a
T ₇	15.6 b	15.8 ab	16.0 ab	16.3ab		15.3 b	15.5 b	16.0 ab	16.7 ab
T ₈	15.6 b	15.9 ab	17.0 ab	18.0a		15.6 b	16.0 ab	16.6 ab	17.3 ab
T ₉	16.0 ab	16.6 ab	17.3 ab	18.3 a		15.0 b	15.3 b	16.0 ab	17.0 ab
T ₁₀	16.0 ab	16.6 ab	17.6 ab	180.6 a		16.2 ab	16.4 ab	17.3 ab	18.3 a

- T₁ = control
- T₂ = boric acid 1%
- T₃ = boric acid 2%
- T₄ = abscisic acid 1%
- T₅ = abscisic acid 2%
- T₆ = rosemary oil 1%
- T₇ = rosemary 2%
- T₈ = camphor oil 1%
- T₉ = camphor 2%
- T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

Table 7: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils for on Total Acidity Percentage on Crimson Seedless Grape at Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

Acid (%)									
Season	2019					2020			
Period in days									
Treatments	H	2	4	6		H	2	4	6
T ₁	0.66 b	0.63 b	0.57 f	0.49 i		0.68 b	0.63 f	0.59 j	0.53 n
T ₂	0.65 b	0.64 b	0.59 e	0.52		0.65 d	0.62 g	0.58 k	0.51 p
T ₃	0.64 b	0.60 d	0.56 f	0.43		0.64 e	0.61 h	0.56 l	0.51 p
T ₄	0.69 ab	0.62 c	0.58 f	0.49 i		0.66 d	0.62 g	0.57 l	0.52 o
T ₅	0.75 a	0.70 ab	0.63 b	0.59 e		0.73 ab	0.67 c	0.62 g	0.55 m
T ₆	0.74 ab	0.68 ab	0.61 d	0.52 h		0.74 ab	0.69 ab	0.65 d	0.56 l
T ₇	0.76 a	0.70 ab	0.63 b	0.57 f		0.75 a	0.69 ab	0.63 f	0.52 n
T ₈	0.66 b	0.61 d	0.54 g	0.49 i		0.70 ab	0.71 ab	0.64 e	0.56 l
T ₉	0.65 b	0.64 b	0.56 f	0.49 i		0.68 b	0.64 e	0.58 k	0.51 p
T ₁₀	0.64 b	0.59 e	0.51 h	0.46 j		0.69 ab	0.67 c	0.62 g	0.58 k

T₁ = control

T₂ = boric acid 1%

T₃ = boric acid 2%

T₄ = abscisic acid 1%

T₅ = abscisic acid 2%

T₆ = rosemary oil 1%

T₇ = rosemary 2%

T₈ = camphor oil 1%

T₉ = camphor 2%

T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

Table 8: Effect of Using Some Nutrients and Essential Oils for on S.S.C/Acid ratio on Crimson Seedless Grape at Shelf Life Period During 2019 and 2020 Seasons

S.S.C/Acid ratio								
Season	2019					2020		
Period in days								
Treatments	H	2	4	6		H	2	4
T ₁	24.88 i	25.53 h	29.5 f	36.28 ab		22.62 e	25.42 d	27.65
T ₂	26.66 h	25.72 h	28.58 g	33.16 c		23.96 e	25.65 d	29.62 bc
T ₃	24.81 i	23.94 j	29.91 f	35.84 ab		23.71 e	25.73 d	28.30 c
T ₄	22.48 j	25.02 i	29.88 f	40.14 a		24.28 d	24.95 d	28.52 c
T ₅	20.46 l	22.29	27.13 h	30.22 e		21.48 h	23.3 e	26.13 cd
T ₆	21.68 k	24.56 i	28.72 g	35.17b		21.02 h	22.98 e	25.04 d
T ₇	20.41 l	25.96 h	26.99 h	31.41 d		20.26 g	22.36 e	25.29 d
T ₈	23.49 j	26.06 h	31.08 d	36.80 ab		22.20 e	21.41 f	25.98 d
T ₉	24.16 i	26.01 h	30.93 e	36.70 ab		22.10 e	23.97 e	27.70 cd
T ₁₀	24.77 i	28.18 g	34.54 c	40.84 a		23.45 e	25.15 d	28.66 c

- T₁ = control
- T₂ = boric acid 1%
- T₃ = boric acid 2%
- T₄ = abscisic acid 1%
- T₅ = abscisic acid 2%
- T₆ = rosemary oil 1%
- T₇ = rosemary 2%
- T₈ = camphor oil 1%
- T₉ = camphor 2%
- T₁₀ = ethephon 2%

From the present study, it can be concluded that camphor oil and rosemary oil are effective in coloring Crimson seedless grape. The exogenous application of abscisic acid (1% or 2%), boric acid (1% or 2%), rosemary oil (2%), and camphor oil (1% or 2%) significantly improves the color of berries on Crimson seedless grape, particularly at a concentration of in two applications, on version stage and 7 days after version, resulting in clusters with greater consumer acceptance through visual-sensory analysis. Regardless of the concentration or application timing, there is no change in the physicochemical characteristics of the berries or clusters.

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